

Reaction to BPH biotype 2 of wild rice lines originating from *Oryza officinalis*.^a IRRRI, 1989.

Variety	Damage rating ^b
IR54742-1-11-17-12-3	1
IR54742-1-11-17-26-2	1
IR54742-1-11-17-26-3	1
IR54742-1-17-12-26-2	1
IR54742-1-17-20-8-1	3
IR54742-1-17-20-8-3	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-1	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-2	1
IR54742-1-18-12-11-3	1
IR54742-5-36-4-17-1	3
IR54742-5-36-4-17-3	3
IR54742-6-20-3-9-2	1
IR54742-6-20-3-9-3	1
IR54742-6-20-3-22-2	1
IR54742-6-20-3-22-3	3
IR54742-11-1-9-15-2	1
IR54742-11-2-8-2-1	3
IR54742-11-2-8-2-3	3
IR54742-11-17-10-5-2	3
IR54742-18-17-20-15-3	3
IR54742-22-14-24-22-2	3
IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	3
IR54742-22-19-3-15-1	3
IR54742-23-11-19-6-1	1
IR54742-23-11-19-6-3	1
IR54742-23-19-16-12-1	3
IR54742-23-19-16-12-2	1
IR54742-23-19-16-12-3	1
IR54742-31-9-26-15-2	3
IR54742-31-21-20-10-2	3
IR54742-33-18-20-3-2	3
IR54742-33-18-20-3-3	1
IR54742-38-13-15-2-2	3
IR54742-38-26-10-17-1	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-1	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-2	1
IR54742-41-15-30-23-3	1
IR54742-41-40-20-19-1	3
IR54742-4140-20-19-2	3
IR54745-2-2-25-26-1	1
IR54745-2-2-25-26-3	1
IR.54745-2-10-17-8-2	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-1	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-2	3
IR54745-2-21-12-17-4	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-5	1
IR54745-2-21-12-17-6	1
IR54745-2-23-19-8-1	1
IR54745-2-23-19-8-2	3
IR54745-2-23-19-8-3	1
IR.54745-2-28-22-7-2	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-1	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-2	1
IR54745-2-37-5-26-3	1
IR54745-2-45-3-24-2	1
IR54748-1-17-12-1	1
IR54748-1-17-12-3	1
IR54748-1-17-25-3	1
IR54742-9-44	3
IR54742-9-4-5	1
IR54742-19-2-3	1
IR74 (resistant check)	1
TN1 (susceptible check)	9

^a Av of 3 replications. All entries, except TN1 showed resistance. ^b By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Leaffolder (LF) damage and yield loss on some selected rice varieties

S. K. Shrivastava, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Jagdalpur 494005, Madhya Pradesh (MP), India (present address: IERP [IGKVV], c/o Dy. Director of Agriculture, Durg 491001, M.P., India)

We studied the effect of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Gueneé infestation on panicle length and weight during 1987 wet season.

Kranti, Madhuri, Mahsuri, Asha, Gurmatia, Safri 17, Makdo, and CR1014 were transplanted in 5- × 4.60-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The crop was fertilized at 40-30-20 kg NPK/ha.

After flag leaf emergence, 15 hills

of each variety were selected at random. Infested and healthy leaves were counted. Panicle length and panicle weight were measured at harvest.

The data suggested that all the varieties were susceptible to LF (see table). The degree of susceptibility was in order Kranti > Mahsuri > Madhuri > Asha > Gurmatia > Safri 17 > Makdo > CR1014.

Correlations indicated that the higher the infestation, the shorter the panicle length and the lighter the panicle weight. But correlation coefficients were significant only between leaf damage and panicle weight in Gurmatia and Safri 17 and only between leaf damage and panicle length in CR1014, Kranti, and Madhuri. □

LF damage and yield of selected rice varieties. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1987 wet season.

Variety	Leaf damage (%)	Panicle wt (g)		Panicle length (cm)		Correlation ^a	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Damage-panicle wt	Damage-panicle length
CR1014	12.21	2.00-2.56	2.17	16.01-19.01	17.07	-0.30	-0.78*
Kranti	24.63	1.52-2.30	1.87	17.01-20.09	18.08	-0.18	-0.63*
Mahsuri	24.32	2.59-2.79	2.26	15.08-17.04	16.05	-0.45	-0.47
Gurmatia	15.96	1.43-1.83	1.64	17.06-21.01	17.09	-0.98*	-0.19
Safri 17	15.13	0.86-1.01	0.94	16.03-17.03	16.08	-0.68*	-0.27
Madhuri	23.46	1.73-1.96	1.81	17.06-22.05	20.09	-0.23	-0.52*
Asha	16.52	1.68-2.14	1.87	16.01-20.05	19.07	-0.41	-0.48
Makdo	13.39	1.96-2.30	2.22	15.03-18.03	16.04	-0.39	-0.14

^a* = significant at the 0.05 level.

Adverse soils tolerance

Performance of selected rice genotypes in alkaline, saline, and normal soils and their interaction with climate factors

J. E. Marassi, M. Collado, R. Benavidez, and M. J. Arturi, CIC, Prov. Bs. As.; and J. J. N. Marassi, Central Experiment Station, Faculty of Agronomy, La Plata National University, CC 46, Suc. 6, La Plata (1900), Argentina

Soil salinity and alkalinity associated with low temperature are the major problems of the coastal area of the Salado River basin, Buenos Aires Province.

We evaluated 81 cultivars and 9 local lines and varieties for alkalinity and salinity tolerance, under temperate climate conditions (35° south latitude).

The severely deteriorated alkali soil (Typic Natraqualf) of the Salado River basin is characterized by high pH (9.6), sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage exceeding 60), calcium carbonate precipitation, clay texture. Soil salinity was created artificially by adding NaCl to 8 dS/m at seeding. Normal soil was a Typic Argiudoll with excellent agronomic characteristics.

Entries were dry seeded in problem soils 1 and 2 Oct 1987 and in